

S P A T I A L

GUIDING LIGHT IN THE AI LANDSCAPE

Illuminating the Path to a Trustworthy AI Ecosystem

When?

1st July 2024

At what time?

From 10:00 AM -17:00 PM CET

Where?

Faculty of Technology, Policy & Management
TU Delft, Jaffalaan 5, 2628BX, Delft, Netherlands

The final event invites participants from academic institutions and industry partners to discuss the present and future of Trustworthy AI, build their networks, and present their own research in poster sessions.

REGISTER HERE!

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